

Original Article

STRATEGIES FOR UPGRADING TEACHER EDUCATION IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract

The study determined strategies for upgrading teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State. Three specific purposes and corresponding research questions guided the study. The researchers adopted a descriptive survey research design for the study. Population for the study consisted of all 423 teacher educators from public colleges of education in Enugu State from which 100 respondents were sampled. Instrument for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire developed by the researchers and titled "Strategies for upgrading teacher education (SUTE)". The instrument contained 18 items in three clusters based on the three research questions with the options of strongly agree (SA), agree (A) disagree (D) strongly disagree (SD). Three experts in Enugu State College of Education (Technical), Enugu validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.78, 0.81 and 0.79 for clusters 1-3 respectively with an overall reliability index of 0.79 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. Mean statistics was used to answer the research questions and decision was based on the cluster mean score in relation to a cut off mean score of 2.50. Findings of the study revealed among others that inadequate funding is a major challenge facing teacher education, providing ongoing professional development opportunities can upgrade teacher education and technology facilitates collaboration among teacher educators and students. Based on these findings, the researchers concluded that there is a great need for the government to upgrade teacher education in Enugu state in order to raise the standard of education especially at college of education that produce teachers for the foundation levels of education. It was recommended that the stake holders of colleges of education should improve on the rate at which fund is approved and release for teacher education, and organize continuous professional development programmes to enhance lecturers' proficiency in teaching of their various courses in their various area of specialization.

Keywords: Strategies, Upgrading, Teacher Education, Technology Integration, Professional Development and Lecturers' Proficiency.

Introduction

Teacher education is a critical component of any country's education system as it plays a vital role in shaping the quality of education and the future of the nation (UNESCO, 2014). In Nigeria, according to Federal Ministry of Education (2013), teacher

education has been identified as a key area of concern, with numerous challenges affecting the quality of teacher preparation and professional development. Research has consistently shown that teacher quality is a critical factor in determining student learning outcomes (Hanushek, 2011;

Darling-Hammond, 2017). Teachers who are well-prepared and supported are more likely to produce students who achieve better academic outcomes (Rockoff, 2004).

The importance of teacher education in Nigeria cannot be overstated because, according to Hanushek (2011), teachers are the backbone of the education system, and their quality has a direct impact on student learning outcomes. However, the current state of teacher education in Nigeria is characterized by inadequate infrastructure, outdated curriculum, and insufficient funding (National Commission for Colleges of Education, 2015). Okebukola (2015) averred that these challenges have resulted in a shortage of qualified teachers, particularly in rural and disadvantaged areas. World Bank (2018) reported that despite efforts to reform teacher education in Nigeria, the country still faces significant challenges in providing high-quality education to its citizens. Therefore, it is very essential to upgrade teacher education in Nigeria in order to improve student learning outcomes by adequately addressing the observed challenges. To effectively address the challenges facing teacher education in Nigeria, there is a need to determine suitable strategies to upgrade teacher education programmes especially in colleges of education. According to Darling-Hammond (2017), such strategies should focus on improving the quality of teacher preparation, providing ongoing professional development opportunities, and enhancing the overall teaching and learning environment. Teacher preparation and professional development are critical components of teacher education. Research has shown that teachers who participate in high-quality professional development programmes are more likely to improve their teaching practices and produce better student outcomes. However, National Commission for Colleges of Education (2015) posited that teacher preparation and professional development programmes in Nigeria are often

inadequate and ineffective. These programmes require urgent upgrade through technology integration to produce high quality teachers that can function at the same level with others globally. Technology integration in teacher education has been identified as a potential solution for improving teacher quality and student learning outcomes (Koehler & Mishra, 2009). Mishra and Koehler (2006) observed that technology can provide teachers with access to high-quality professional development opportunities, enhance their teaching practices, and improve student engagement and motivation. According to World Bank (2018), upgrading of teacher education can improve the quality of education system, increase student learning outcomes, and ultimately drive economic growth and development to a higher level. Several countries have implemented innovative teacher education programmes that have improved teacher quality and student learning outcomes. For example, Sahlberg, (2011) posited that Finland's teacher education program is highly regarded for its emphasis on teacher preparation and professional development. Singapore's teacher education program is also notable for its focus on teacher quality and student outcomes according to OECD, (2011). Social Cognitive Theory propounded by Bandura, (1986) posits that learning is a cognitive process that occurs in a social context, where individuals learn by observing, imitating, and modelling behaviours. In the context of teacher education, this theory suggests that teachers learn and adopt new teaching methods and technologies by observing and imitating others. Teacher Professional Development Theory propounded by Guskey, (2000) emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers to improve their teaching practices and student learning outcomes. It suggests that teacher professional development should be a

continuous process that addresses the changing needs of teachers and students. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) Theory propounded by Mishra & Koehler, (2006) proposes that teachers need to develop a deep understanding of the intersection of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge

To effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. It suggests that teachers should develop a nuanced understanding of how to use technology to support student learning.

Despite the extensive research on teacher education, there is a need for a comprehensive study that examines the strategies for upgrading teacher education in Nigeria. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the challenges facing teacher education in Nigeria and identifying strategies for improving teacher quality and student learning outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Teacher education system is confronted with numerous challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, outdated curriculum, and insufficient funding, resulting in a shortage of qualified teachers, particularly in rural and disadvantaged areas (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013; NCCE, (2015). According to World Bank, (2018). These challenges has led to poor student learning outcomes, low educational attainment, and a lack of competitiveness in the global economy

Teacher education system in Nigeria is characterized by inadequate teacher preparation and professional development opportunities, limited access to quality teacher education programs, ineffective teacher deployment and utilization strategies, low teacher motivation and morale, and inadequate teacher evaluation and accountability mechanisms (Okebukola, 2015; UNESCO, 2014). Moreover, Hanushek, (2011) stated that these challenges have significant implications for Nigeria's economic and social development, as a well-

educated and skilled workforce is essential for driving growth, innovation, and competitiveness.

The problem of this study, therefore, is that teacher education programmes in higher educational institutions in Nigeria generally and colleges of education in Enugu in particular are not producing good quality teachers for effective curriculum implementation. Specifically, teacher education programme in colleges of education in Enugu State is facing several challenges resulting in poor quality teachers for primary and secondary education. This problem is negatively affecting social and economic development of the populace and the state necessitating an urgent upgrade of the programme by adequately tackling the highlighted challenges. However, suitable strategies for the programme upgrading appear not be clearly known. Therefore, this study on strategies for upgrading teacher education programme in colleges of education in Enugu State is imperative as it would provide empirical data that would guide objective remedial actions by relevant stakeholders.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine suitable strategies for upgrading teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify the major challenges facing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State.
2. Determine whether improving teacher preparation with adequate professional Development programs can upgrade teacher education quality in colleges of education in Enugu state.
3. Determine whether technology integration can upgrade teacher education programme in Colleges of education in Enugu state.

Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the major challenges facing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu state?
2. In what ways can teacher preparation with adequate professional development programmes upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State?
3. In what ways can technology integration upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu state?

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research since it allows for the collection of data from a large sample of participants to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem according to Creswell (2014). In addition, Babbie (2016) explained that descriptive survey enables researchers to identify patterns, trends, and relationships among variables, which are essential for policy decisions and practice.

Population for the study consisted of all 423 teacher educators from public colleges of education in Enugu State from which 100 respondents were

Results

Table 1: Respondents mean ratings on the major challenges facing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State.

S/N	Items statements: The major challenges include:	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Inadequate funding	3.45	Agree
2	Lack of infrastructure and instructional resources	3.32	Agree
3	Welfare of lecturers is neglected by the government	3.00	Agree
4	The curriculum does not align with the realities of the 21st century.	3.03	Agree
5	Professional development programmes are inadequate	3.06	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.17	Agree

Table 1 shows that the mean ratings for each of the five challenges is above the cut-off mean score of 2.50 which means that the respondents agreed that they are the major challenges facing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State.

Table 2: Respondents’ mean ratings on how teacher preparation with adequate professional development programmes can upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State.

sampled using stratified simple random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire developed by the researchers and titled “Strategies for upgrading teacher education (SUTE)”. The instrument contained 18 items in three clusters based on the three research questions with the options of strongly agree (SA), agree (A) disagree (D) strongly disagree (SD). Three experts in Enugu State College of Education (Technical), Enugu validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.78, 0.81 and 0.79 for clusters 1- 3 respectively with an overall reliability index of 0.79 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. It was used to collect data from a sample of teacher educators from the public colleges of education in Enugu state. Mean statistics was used to answer the research questions and decision was based on the cluster mean score in relation to a cut off mean score of 2.50

The grand mean of 3.17 confirms that teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State is facing several serious challenges which are negating its quality.

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Improving teacher preparation programs is essential for upgrading teacher education in Nigeria.	2.88	Agree
2	Providing ongoing professional development opportunities is important for upgrading teacher education in Nigeria.	3.82	Agree
3	Prompt approval for and release of fund for professional development programmes can improve the quality of teacher education	3.20	Agree
4	Enhancing teacher motivation and welfare is crucial for upgrading teacher education in Nigeria.	3.44	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.08	Agree

Table 2 shows the Mean ratings of teacher educators on how teacher preparation and professional development programs can be improved to enhance quality of teacher education in Colleges of Education in Enugu State. All the 4 items have mean above the

cut-off which yielded a grand mean of 3.08 thus indicating that they were supported by the teacher educators to be ways of effectively improving teacher educators in colleges of education in Enugu state.

Table 3: Respondents’ Mean ratings on the role that technology can play in enhancing teacher education in Enugu State

SN	Items	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Integrating technology into teacher education programs is necessary for upgrading teacher education in Nigeria.	3.15	Agree
2	Technology can make teacher effective through Online courses	3.34	Agree
3	Developing technology-integrated curricula can enhance teacher education in Nigeria	3.04	Agree
4	Mobile apps can be applied in teacher education program to improve its teaching and learning process.	2.72	Agree
5	Social media is one of the technology that could help in improving the condition of Nigeria teacher education to a greater height when appropriately used.	3.22	Agree
6	Technology will improve the quality of teacher education programs in Nigeria if the required infrastructure is provided.	3.39	Agree
7	Technology increases access to teacher education programs for rural areas in Nigeria.	3.25	Agree
8	Technology tools can enhance teacher educators' productivity in Nigeria.	3.37	Agree
9	Technology facilitates collaboration among teacher educators and students in Nigeria	2.81	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.14	Agree

Table 3 shows the mean ratings of teacher educators on role that technology play in enhancing teacher education in Colleges of Education in Enugu State. All the 9 items have mean above the cut-off which yielded a grand mean of 3.14 thus indicating that

they were supported by the teacher educators to be role that technology play in enhancing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu state.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that inadequate funding is a major challenge facing teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State. This finding agrees with the report of the National Commission for Colleges of Education, (2015) which stated that current state of teacher education in Nigeria is characterized by inadequate infrastructure, outdated curriculum, and insufficient funding. In addition, the study found that improving teacher preparation with adequate professional development programmes can upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State. This finding is in line with Okebukola, (2015) and UNESCO, (2014) which indicated that current teacher education system in Nigeria is characterized by inadequate teacher preparation and professional development opportunities. Teacher Professional Development Theory propounded by Guskey, (2000) also emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers to improve their teaching practices and student learning outcomes. This finding suggests that teacher professional development should be a continuous process that addresses the changing needs of teachers and students. Furthermore, findings of the study revealed that technology integration can upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State because technology utilization facilitates collaboration among teacher educators and students. The finding is in line with Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) Theory propounded by Mishra & Koehler, (2006) which proposes that teachers need to develop a deep understanding of the intersection of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. This suggests that teachers should develop a nuanced understanding of how to use technology to support student learning. Therefore, technology can play

important role in upgrading teacher education in Colleges of Education in Enugu State.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu State is facing several grave challenges which negatively affect the quality of the product and that improving teacher preparation with adequate professional development programmes and technology integration can lead to an upgrade. Based on these findings, the researchers concluded that there is a great need for the government to upgrade teacher education in colleges of education in Enugu state in order to raise the quality of teachers for the foundational levels of education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The government should improve on the rate at which fund is approved and release for teacher education.
- ii. The management team of colleges of education should organize continuous professional development programmes to enhance lecturers' proficiency in teaching of their various courses in their various area of specialization.
- iii. Also the advanced technological tools with uninterrupted power supply should be made available by the government to enable the lecturers learn and continue to learn by practicing regularly which will make them experts and improve the poor condition of teacher education in Enugu state.
- iv. The curriculum developers should improve the teacher education curriculum to align with the realities of the 21st century.
- v. Professional bodies within teacher education should mandate their members to integrate technology in delivering their lectures in order to upgrade teacher education in their various fields

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